

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of work competence, work motivation and work environment on employee performance at Depo-MA Sidoarjo, Indonesia

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Abstract

This study looked at Depo-MA Sidoarjo in Indonesia to see how job competency, work motivation, and work environment effect employee performance. The research followed a quantitative approach and involved 50 participants. The sampling technique used was saturated sampling, which included distributing questionnaires, conducting interviews, and making observations. Classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression, and hypothesis testing were used to examine the data. According to the data collected using SPSS 22, employee performance is favorably and significantly influenced by job competence and work environment, but not by work motivation. The results of the F-test demonstrated that job competence, work motivation, and work environment all together had a significant impact on employee performance, with work competence being the most influential factor at Depo-MA Sidoarjo. This study contributes to the ongoing discussion on the relationship between these variables.

Keywords: Employee Performance; Work Competence; Work Environment; Work Motivation

1. Introduction

Managing a company requires the utmost importance placed on human resources as they play a crucial role in driving all aspects of the organization. The presence of skilled and high-performing employees is essential for the success of the company, as the absence of capable human resources would hinder its operations. Conversely, the presence of incompetent and underperforming employees poses significant challenges that can lead the company towards financial losses.

According to [1]; [2], in addition to its involvement in utilization, development, management, and performance planning, human resource management also has a vital role in improving performance. For this system to operate effectively, management must give careful consideration to various significant factors, including competence, motivation, work environment, performance, and other related aspects.

Competence refers to the employees' capability to fulfill company requirements, as well as their expertise and professional needs [3]. It entails individuals having superior, consistent, and efficient abilities beyond general performance [4]. Competence holds significant importance in organizational management as it is closely linked to outstanding work performance. Over time, the concept of competence has evolved into a fixed notion that cannot accurately predict employee performance and success [5]. As stated by [6], competence represents an individual's ability to carry out various assigned tasks by leveraging all their skills to meet job demands. The competencies possessed by employees have a direct impact on their performance [7]; [8]; [9]. When employees possess the required competence, they are more likely to enhance their performance.

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Motivation can be interpreted as a situation in which an employee can develop all of his abilities to work even harder. If he wants something, then he will be compelled to do certain activities to get what he wants. According to research [10]. Employee job happiness is greatly influenced by work motivation. Work motivation has a positive and significant impact on enhancing employee performance [11].

Apart from competence and work motivation, the work environment is another factor that can potentially influence employee performance. As stated by [12], the work environment can be defined as a well-maintained workplace that fosters conditions and situations conducive to enhancing employee motivation in their job responsibilities. A favorable work environment encompasses various aspects, including fostering positive relationships among colleagues, promoting positive interactions between superiors and subordinates, ensuring an appropriate physical work setting (e.g., adequate workspace size, lighting, noise control, cleanliness, and availability of equipment). An unfavorable work environment can lead to employee stress, ultimately resulting in decreased performance. Conversely, companies that prioritize a positive and comfortable work environment has the potential to motivate employees and improve their performance. Additionally, favorable working conditions can reduce boredom and fatigue, thereby positively impacting employee performance. Several studies [12]; [13]; [14] have discovered a strong and advantageous connection between the workplace and performance, highlighting the significance of the appropriate workplace in improving performance. Employee performance is not significantly affected by the workplace environment, according to some research findings, it is important to note [15].

Performance refers to the overall level of achievement exhibited by an employee over a specific period, measured by aligning their tasks with predefined parameters such as standardized activity outcomes, targets, or predetermined qualifications that have been mutually agreed upon. One measure of success for employees is their ability to carry out their responsibilities with a sense of accountability, aiming to accomplish the organization's goals while adhering to its vision, objectives, and targets [16]. With increased repetition of a task, individuals become more proficient and efficient in completing it. Engaging in diverse tasks expands one's work experience and enables them to handle a broader range of responsibilities. Employee performance is the measure of an employee's success in executing and completing their entire set of tasks [13]. If there are no established goals and targets for assessment, it becomes challenging to assess the performance of an individual or an organization without reference points for success. Evaluating the employee's competence in fulfilling their assigned responsibilities can be gauged by their outward performance. Employee performance refers to the degree of accomplishment exhibited by an employee in executing and finalizing a comprehensive set of tasks [13]. Consequently, achieving optimal employee performance can foster the attainment of various organizational or company objectives.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Work Competence

Competence refers to the capacity of employees to effectively perform their tasks in accordance with their capabilities. As stated in [17], competence encompasses various aspects of an individual's abilities, such as knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, or personal traits, which empower workers to achieve favorable outcomes and successful task completion.

[18] states that there are 5 indicators that can measure work competence, namely:

- ability.
- Attitude
- Understanding
- Knowledge
- Interests

2.2. Work motivation

According to [19] work motivation is a competence involving the ability to guide, influence, and inspire individuals towards engaging in desired behaviors aimed at achieving specific objectives. As mentioned in [20], work motivation represents a fundamental human requirement and serves as a motivating force to fulfill essential needs. Consequently, when these needs are present, they contribute to the successful completion of activities. Employees with a strong sense of work motivation will strive to perform their tasks to the best of their abilities.

Herzberg in [21] states that there are 5 indicators that can measure work motivation, namely:

- Recognition
- Achievements
- The work itself
- Advancements
- Responsibility

This indicator shows the extent to which employees feel they have responsibility and autonomy in their work, including opportunities to take initiative, make decisions, and manage their own work time.

2.3. Work environment

The work environment is a commonly utilized setting where employees perform their daily tasks [22]. As stated in [23], the work environment refers to the circumstances surrounding workers while they are fulfilling their job responsibilities which this situation has an influence on workers when doing their work in the context of carrying out company operations. According to [24], the work environment plays a crucial role in shaping employee performance, as it directly impacts their ability to fulfill tasks and, consequently, enhances organizational effectiveness. Employees who can perform their tasks effectively, safely, and comfortably define a positive work environment as one in which they can. Thus, the establishment and cultivation of a positive work environment significantly influence the achievement of organizational goals. Conversely, an unfavorable work environment diminishes motivation and morale, ultimately resulting in reduced employee performance.

There are 5 indicators that measure the work environment according to [25]:

- Facilities/tools in the workplace
- Safety at work
- Temperature / air temperature
- Atmosphere
- Relations between co-workers and superiors

2.4. Employee performance

Performance is the outcome of work accomplished by an individual, reflecting both the quantity and quality of their achievements within a specific timeframe. As stated in [26], performance within the realm of work productivity entails the exploration of potential, making productivity a structured process to uncover the inherent capabilities of an object or entity. Essentially, the philosophy of productivity embodies the aspiration and endeavor of every individual or group to continually enhance their quality of life and livelihood. The definition of performance encompasses the output, in terms of quality and quantity, that an employee attains while fulfilling their duties in alignment with assigned responsibilities. Performance represents the outcome or result of a given process [26].

According to Edison in [23], there are 5 employee performance indicators, namely:

- Quality of work
- The quantity of work
- Honesty
- Level of consistency
- Creativity

Source: composed by author

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

2.5. Hypothesis of Research

There are proposed hypotheses that are mostly based on the problem statement and conceptual framework:

- H1: Work competence (X1) affects employee performance (Y).
- H2: Work motivation (X2) affects employee performance (Y).
- H3: Work environment (X3) affects employee performance (Y).
- H4: Work competence, work motivation and work environment affect employee performance.

3. Method

Using quantitative research methods for this study, as mentioned in [27]. Quantitative research methods are utilized to investigate populations or randomly selected samples, involving the use of research instruments for data collection and statistical analysis to test predetermined hypotheses. Primary and secondary data sources are utilized in this research.

The study includes all employees of Depo-MA Sidoarjo as the target population. A saturated sample was employed as the sampling technique, where every employee is included in the sample. This approach is suitable when the total population is below 100 or when the researcher aims to minimize errors. Consequently, based on this rationale, the sample size for this study consisted of 50 respondents.

Direct observation, conversations with relevant parties, and ultimately the distribution of questionnaires to Depo-MA Sidoarjo staff were used to gather data. Distributing questionnaires online using Google Form media. Assess the instrument using a Likert scale with alternative answer choices 1-5 with the following statements.

Table 1 A Likert scale

Symbol	Description	Weight/Value
STS	Strongly Disagree	1
TS	Disagree	2
N	Neutral	3
S	Agree	4
SS	Strongly Agree	5

Source: Composed by Author

4. Results

4.1. Validity Test

Table 2 Result of validity test

Instrument	r-cont	r-table	Remark
X1.1	0.7855	0.2787	Valid
X1.2	0.8667	0.2787	Valid
X1.3	0,7708	0.2787	Valid
X1.4	0.7971	0.2787	Valid
X1.5	0.7892	0.2787	Valid
X2.1	0.8977	0.2787	Valid
X2.2	0.8895	0.2787	Valid
X2.3	0.7897	0.2787	Valid
X2.4	0.8521	0.2787	Valid

X2.5	0.707	0.2787	Valid
X3.1	0.8045	0.2787	Valid
X3.2	0.9072	0.2787	Valid
X3.3	0.8695	0.2787	Valid
X3.4	0.9336	0.2787	Valid
X3.5	0.8114	0.2787	Valid
Y1	0.7988	0.2787	Valid
Y2	0.9049	0.2787	Valid
Y3	0.8249	0.2787	Valid
Y4	0.8727	0.2787	Valid
Y5	0.8559	0.2787	Valid

Source: SPSS output

Each item in the statements shows a correlation coefficient (r count) that surpasses the critical value (r table). Hence, according to the validity test results, it follows that any statement made about the four variables under study are taken as valid and appropriate as research instruments.

4.2. Reliability Test

Table 3 Result of reliability test

Variable	Cronbach's alpha	Standard	Remark
Work Competence	0.859	0.6	Reliable
Work Motivation	0.885	0.6	Reliable

SPSS output

According to the reliability test results, the work competency variable's Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is 0.859, the work motivation variable's is 0.885, the work environment variable's is 0.913, and the employee performance variable's is 0.903. These values exceed the threshold of 0.6, indicating high reliability. Therefore, the data collected in this study is considered suitable for further analysis.

4.3. Classic assumption test

4.3.1. Normality test

Table 4 Result of normality test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		50
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.83002939
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	0.089
		0.069
	Negative	-0.089
Test Statistic		0.089
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.200

Source: SPSS output

The Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value, according to the provided table, is 0.200. Given that the significance level is greater than 0.05, this suggests that the regression model follows a normal distribution. It is implied that the data has a normal distribution when the decision-making criteria listed in the aforementioned Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for normalcy are taken into account. As a result, the regression model's presumptions or requirements for normalcy have been satisfied.

4.3.2. Multicollinearity Test

Table 5 Result of multicollinearity test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	2.234	1.448		1.542	0.130		
Work Competence	0.649	0.149	0.652	4.348	0.000	0.218	4.581
Work Motivation	-0.097	0.125	-0.108	-0.780	0.439	0.255	3.923
Work Environment	0.327	0.139	0.352	2.347	0.023	0.219	4.571

Source: SPSS output

The results of the tolerance calculation show that Work Competence (X1) has a tolerance value of 0.218, Work Motivation (X2) has a tolerance value of 0.255, and Work Environment (X3) has a tolerance value of 0.219. These values are all above 0.10, suggesting no significant correlation exists among the independent variables. Additionally, the Variant Inflation Factor (VIF) values are computed as follows: Work Competence (X1) with a VIF of 4.581, Work Motivation (X2) with a VIF of 3.923, and Work Environment (X3) with a VIF of 4.571. All three variables have values below 10. Thus, it may be said that the regression model's independent variables do not exhibit multicollinearity.

4.3.3. Heteroscedasticity Test

To evaluate whether heteroscedasticity is present, the heteroscedasticity test examines a certain pattern on the scatterplot between standardized residuals and expected values. The projected Y values are shown on the Y-axis in this scatterplot, while the residuals are shown on the X-axis.

Source: SPSS output

Figure 2 Scatter Plot

Observing the Scatterplot output, it is evident that the dots are dispersed without exhibiting a distinct wave-like pattern of expanding and contracting. Thus, it can be inferred that the data used in this study does not exhibit any issues with heteroscedasticity.

4.4. Hypothesis test

4.4.1. Partial Test (t-Test)

Table 6 Result of t-Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.234	1.448		1.542	0.130
	Work Competence	0.649	0.149	0.652	4.348	0.000
	Work Motivation	-0.097	0.125	-0.108	-0.780	0.439
	Work Environment	0.327	0.139	0.352	2.347	0.023

Source: SPSS output

To determine the significance level based on the t-table, it is crucial to calculate the degrees of freedom using the formula $n-k$, where n is 50 and k is 4, resulting in 46 degrees of freedom. The t-table reveals a value of 2.01290 at a significance level of α : 0.05 for 46 degrees of freedom.

As indicated by the table above:

- Work Competency (X1)

The calculated t value of 4.348 is greater than the essential table t value of 2.012, and the significant value of 0.000 is less than 0.05. Therefore, the first hypothesis is accepted. It was concluded that work competence has a positive and significant impact on employee performance.

- Work Motivation (X2)

The t-count value of -0.780 is lower than the crucial t-table value of 2.012, and the significant value of 0.439 is greater than 0.05. This shows that the motivation variable has no significant effect on employee performance variables. Second hypothesis is rejected.

- Work Environment (X3)

The calculated t value of 2.347 is greater than the t table value of 2.012, and the significance value of 0.023 is lower than 0.05. The third hypothesis is accepted. Shows that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

4.4.2. Simultaneous test (F-Test)

Table 7 Result of F-Test

Model		Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	561.899	3	187.300	52.503	0.000
	Residual	164.101	46	3.567		
	Total	726.000	49			

Source: SPSS output

We can use the F-table and its formula $F(k-1; n-k)$, where k stands for the number of variables and n for the total sample size, to estimate the significance level. $F(4-1; 50-4)$ becomes $F(3; 46)$ in this scenario. The essential F-value at a significance level of 0.05 is 2.81, according to the F-table. We see an achieved F-value of 52.503 when performing hypothesis testing using the F-statistic, exceeding the threshold limit of 2.81. Additionally, the significant value (Sig.) is

estimated as 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Consider the factors work environment (X3), work motivation (X2), and work competence (X1). Therefore, it is clear that the combination of work environment, work motivation, and work competence has a significant impact on employee performance.

4.5. Dominant Test

Table 8 Result of dominant test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.234	1.448		1.542	0.130
	Work Competence	0.649	0.149	0.652	4.348	0.000
	Work Motivation	-0.097	0.125	-0.108	-0.780	0.439
	Work Environment	0.327	0.139	0.352	2.347	0.023

Source: SPSS output

Work Competence is the factor in this study that has the biggest impact, as shown by a value of 0.649 and a P-value of 0.000. Therefore, the Work Competence variable demonstrates the most prominent impact on employee performance. The p-value for Work Competence (X1) is less than 0.05 (0.000), indicating its highest level of significance. Furthermore, the β value of 0.649 for Work Competence is the largest among all other variables in relation to employee performance, so it is determined to be the most dominant variable in this study.

4.6. R- Square Test (Coefficient of Determination)

Table 9 Result of 4.6. R- Square

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.880	0.774	0.759	1.88876

Source: SPSS output

The test results are displayed in the table that is included, and it is obvious from it that the aspects of work competence, work motivation, and work environment significantly affect employee performance. The R Square for this relationship is 0.774. A more important overall effect is indicated by a larger R Square value. The variables of work competence, work motivation, and work environment together have an influence of 75.9% on employee performance, according to the Adjusted R Square value of 0.759. The remaining 24.1% of the variance is attributable to other variables that were not considered in this study.

5. Discussion

5.1. Effect of Work Competence on Employee Performance

The first hypothesis test findings show that work competence has a favorable effect on employees' performance at Depo-MA Sidoarjo. According to Table 6, the obtained coefficient is a t-value of 4.348, while the critical t-value from the table is 2.012. By comparing these values, we find that the obtained t-value (4.348) is greater than the critical t-value (2.012), indicating $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table} = 4.348 > 2.012$. Additionally, the significance level (sig.) with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.000$ is lower than 0.05. Therefore, we can conclude that H1 is accepted, while H0 (null hypothesis) is rejected. This suggests that, when taken into account individually, the regression coefficient for the work competency variable has a statistically significant impact on the output of Depo-MA Sidoarjo employee.

Work competence includes the knowledge, skills and abilities possessed by employees in carrying out their job duties and responsibilities. A high level of work competence will enable employees to do their job well, efficiently and effectively. Employees who have strong work competencies will be better able to face job challenges, make the right decisions, and make a significant contribution to performance results.

5.2. The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

The results of the second hypothesis test indicate that work motivation has a negative impact on the performance of Depo-MA Sidoarjo employees. According to Table 6, the obtained coefficient is a t-value of -0.780, while the critical t-value from the table is 2.012. By comparing these values, we find that the obtained t-value (-0.780) is less than the critical t-value (2.012), indicating $t\text{-count} < t\text{-table} = -0.780 < 2.012$. Moreover, the comparison of the significance values with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.439$ shows that it is greater than 0.05. Hence, we can conclude that H2 (alternative hypothesis) is rejected, while H0 (null hypothesis) is accepted. This implies that the regression coefficient for the work motivation variable does not have a statistically significant effect on the performance of Depo-MA Sidoarjo employees when examined individually.

Work motivation includes internal and external factors that encourage employees to achieve goals and improve their performance. High motivation can affect the level of courage, effort, and dedication of employees in carrying out work tasks. Strong work motivation can increase productivity and quality of work, as well as encourage employees to achieve the set targets. If there is no visible influence between motivation on performance, it is necessary to look for another approach that can ensure the effect of motivation on performance

5.3. Effect of Work Environment on Employee Performance

According to the third hypothesis test's findings, the Depo-MA Sidoarjo employees' performance is positively impacted by their working environment. Table 6 shows that the calculated coefficient has a t-value of 2.347, while the crucial t-value is 2.012 in the same table. By comparing these values, we find that the obtained t-value (2.347) is greater than the critical t-value (2.012), indicating $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table} = 2.347 > 2.012$. Additionally, the comparison of the significance values with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.023$ shows that it is less than 0.05. Therefore, we can conclude that H3 is accepted. This implies that the regression coefficient when analyzed separately, the work environment variable has a statistically significant impact on the performance of Depo-MA Sidoarjo employees.

The work environment includes the physical, social, and psychological aspects of the workplace. A good work environment will provide the necessary support, facilities and resources for employees to carry out their duties. A positive and conducive work environment can create a sense of comfort, security and job satisfaction for employees. This can have a positive impact on morale, collaboration and effective communication among employees, which in turn can improve their performance.

5.4. The Effect of Work Competence, Work Motivation and Work Environment Simultaneously on Employee Performance

The findings in table 7 show that the work environment, work motivation, and work competence have a significant and concurrent effect on employee performance. The fact that the observed F value is higher than the critical F value and the significance value (sig.) is 0.000 or less than 0.05 supports this. The F-table value, 2.81, is lower than the calculated F value, 52,503, which is greater. So, it can be stated that the fourth hypothesis is accepted. This shows how factors such as work motivation, work competence, and work environment all have statistically significant regression coefficients that affect how well Depo-MA Sidoarjo employees perform in their jobs.

5.5. The Effect of Work Competence, Work Motivation and Work Environment Dominantly on Employee Performance

According to the findings in table 8, the work competence variable (X1) has the most significant value with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Additionally, it has the largest β coefficient of 0.649 compared to the other variables in relation to employee performance. Therefore, the work competence variable (X1) is identified as the most dominant variable in this study.

5.6. Managerial Implication

In addition to providing input for the organization/company. this study also provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between work competence, work motivation and work environment on employee performance.

6. Conclusion

The following conclusions may be drawn from the study's findings and the discussion of how the workplace's atmosphere, motivation, and competence affect employees' performance at Depo-MA Sidoarjo:

- Employee performance is positively and statistically significantly impacted by the work competence variable.
- Employee performance is not much impacted by work motivation.
- Employee performance is positively and statistically significantly influenced by the work environment variable.
- The working environment, work motivation, and skill at work all have a positive and significant impact on employee performance.
- Work competence is the main factor influencing employee performance.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Author wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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